

The ClairCity Liguria Region Action Plan

For citizen-inclusive air quality and carbon policies

Our future with clean air
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ClairCity is an EU research project which aimed to raise awareness about air pollution and carbon emissions in our cities and regions, looking at how our behaviour contributes to the problems and affects the air we breathe. Uniquely, the project put the power in the hands of residents to determine the best local solutions.

Air pollution has decreased in the past decades in Liguria as result of transport and industry policies. Greenhouse gas emissions also have gone down mainly due to a reduction in emissions from industry. However, NO₂ is the most critical pollutant. Mainly caused by road transport, its EU limit values are not met. The Liguria Region does comply with PM10 EU limit values although the number of exceedances of daily limit values across several stations make it a concerning pollutant as well. O₃ is also a problem.

The Region has a wide regional, multi-modal network of local public transport. Two large railway works are underway: one to separate the traffic flows of the metropolitan and local railway system, another to offer an alternative to road transport for the transfer of goods. Buses are being renewed from diesel to Euro 6 and the link-road Gronda project will allow road traffic to flow from one side of Genoa to the other without going through the city centre. Electric mobility is being facilitated through incentives, a public e-bikes sharing system, privately operated e-scooters, and a free-of-cost charging point for e-scooters have been introduced in the city as well. Further, there are plans to revive the municipal bike sharing scheme.

There are regional and European funds for renewables and energy efficiency, Liguria is behind with renewables implementation compared to other regions in Italy. Renewable energy for heating purposes in the Liguria region consists mainly of biomass burning - mostly outside the major urban centres. Several port initiatives are ongoing concerning the electrification of docks and future use of LNG for ships.

In light of this context, ClairCity examined the possible future impacts of citizens' policy preferences and implementation possibilities against these regional targets. By investigating citizens' current behaviours, their preferred future behaviours and their preferred future policy measures, this brief aims to inform policymaking in the Liguria Region.

Our behaviours contribute to air pollution and carbon emissions

Of the ClairCity respondents, 35% always use their car or motorbike/scooter for commuting to work; 29% do so when going shopping and 34% for leisure activities. On the contrary, more than half of the consulted citizens always go to work and shopping by public transport or through active travel.

Citizens also account by far for the highest contribution to the Liguria Region's carbon footprint through residential heating (compared to road transport, industry and services), which is currently powered primarily by natural gas.

Future behaviours are misaligned with city ambition

In the future, 72% of current car users would like to travel to work, to the shops and for leisure purposes by public transport or through active travel.

Meanwhile, citizens currently heating their homes with natural gas, overwhelming wish to switch to renewables. 70% heat homes with gas presently - in the future 61% wish to heat their homes by renewables, and only 20% by gas

The main barriers for not using public transport at present mainly relate to travel time, timetabling, reliability and its availability (coverage). For home heating, barriers relate to home ownership (or lack thereof) and cost.

The full report can be accessed here:
www.claircity.eu/reports.

Preferred future policies

Using the Delphi survey process, workshops, and innovative Skylines game for mobiles, ClairCity asked citizens about the types of policy measures they would support to reduce air pollution and carbon emissions. A total of 1,400 stakeholders, primarily citizens, engaged in this process. While this is sample is not fully representative, it nevertheless gives an indication of local support for policy measures and intentions for behavioural change.

The top policies were then taken forward to a policy workshop for ratification. In terms of policy priorities, policymakers and citizens are aligned regarding the improvement of public transport and its integration with private transport. They are also in favour of promoting vehicle sharing, active travel and electric mobility.

The main barrier to reducing car use and increasing uptake in public transport, according to policymakers, concerns resistance to change transport habits. The expansion cycle paths, pavements and pedestrian areas are currently impeded by perceived limited space, as these modes compete with other uses of roads (parking, car lanes). Meanwhile, concerning changes to energy suppliers, cost, both for the Region and the citizens is seen as a main barrier.

Citizen-led policies

Policy area defined by citizens	Ratified policy measure
1 Improve local public transport and vehicle-sharing	Increase integrated local public transport network use (including shared vehicles), from 25.4% to 31.5% by 2029, and from 31.5% in 2029 to 45% by 2050
2 Improve integration between public transport and private transport	Increase integrated local public transport network use (including shared vehicles), from 25.4% to 31.5% by 2029, and from 31.5% in 2029 to 45% by 2050
3 Ban diesel vehicles and the most polluting motorcycles in the city	Ban diesel cars and light vehicles less than or equal to the EURO 5 category by 2025 in urban areas
4 Encourage electric mobility	Install an adequate number of charging stations for 50% of the circulating electric vehicles (including car sharing) and replace 50% of vehicles circulating in urban areas with electric cars and motorcycles by 2050
5 Encourage active travel	Increase private trips by bicycle or on foot in the metropolitan area from 23.2% in 2029 to 35% in 2050
6 Transfer some goods traffic from road transport to rail transport	Reduction of heavy vehicle traffic by 30% by 2035 and by 50% by 2050
7 Reduction of energy consumption in housing and buildings	Reduction of residential consumption by 10%, and consumption in the service sector by 16% in 2030

The future of the Liguria Regions' air quality and climate

Modellers used the ratified policies to explore future scenarios. The citizen-led (UPS) scenario results in limited additional reductions compared with the Business as Usual (BAU) - current - scenario. This is partly explained by the fact that policymakers chose in various cases to keep the current ambition level for transport and energy measures instead of opting for more ambitious measures proposed by Genoa area citizens.

The additional reduction of NO_x that the UPS generates beyond the BAU is negligible, as the decrease in NO_x from passenger cars is offset by a rebound of NO_x emissions from buses. The UPS does lead to a slight additional reduction of PM emissions than the BAU, however, by 2050 55% of the population could still be exposed to PM₁₀ concentrations above WHO guideline values.

Lives saved

In terms of health: by 2050 the number of premature deaths from air pollution would be reduced by 79% for NO₂, 11% for PM₁₀, and 6% for PM_{2.5} under UPS, with very similar results under BAU.

Cost implications

The net monetary cost effects of the citizens measures vary substantially. However, the overall balance of direct costs of all measures in the citizens' scenario together suggests that a cost effective execution is possible, as measures with a net direct cost to society can be balanced by measures with net revenues. This balance would be even more positive if also the indirect health benefits of improved health of citizens would be added.

Mutual learning

The Liguria Region can serve the other ClairCity case studies as inspiration concerning its Areas of Limited Traffic (ZTL) policies (allowing access to residents of the area, to electric cars, motorbikes and mopeds) and incentives for electric transport.

Cities can also learn from the regions experiences of citizen opposition to ambitious yet contentious policy proposals. Notably, in 2016 the proposed Vespa ban by the Mayor of Genoa generated the social media campaign under the hashtag #lamiavespanonsitocca ("Don't touch my Vespa"). This, along with other reactions from citizens and associations of motorcyclists, managed to block the ban.

ClairCity case studies can inspire the Region in terms of one-ticketing systems; integrated train, bus and bike-rental systems; city and metropolitan area connections; approaches to disincentivise car use (e.g. reducing the number of resident permits) and incentivise cycling (e.g. bike loans, campaigns, e-cycling); and district heating networks. The full suite of ideas can be found in the full report, which accompanies this summary.

Key to the success of of the Region's ambitions for a future with clean air is open communication with citizens, raising their awareness of the health and economic implications of taking positive steps forward, and the coordination between municipalities to facilitate change.

Action plan for a clean air, zero carbon future

Continued public transport improvements alongside measures to discourage car use and finance improvements. A transport card/ticketing system which works for all modes of transport; expanding car-free, pedestrian zones; limiting parking spaces in the city centre of the Liguria Region municipalities; and most importantly, making parking more expensive. Traffic restriction policies, although unpopular, can be seen as an opportunity that can help establish new transport habits. Extra fees could fund further measures. Communication campaigns should be considered for informing citizens about services available, improvements made and explaining the health benefits of discouraging car use.

Develop an urban bike network to facilitate (e-) cycling, integrate with public transport and further facilitate walking. Facilitate (e-)cycling by infrastructural measures such as urban cycle lanes (and lifts) that extend to the places where citizens want to get to on a daily basis. Foster intermodality by allowing (e-)bikes on public transport as well as offering bike rental at popular train and bus stations. In order to make cycling safer, cycling traffic lights and bike parking facilities should be implemented. Boost walking through increased space for pedestrians and expansion of pedestrian-only zones and equip pedestrian zones with electrical mini-taxis for citizens who may need motorised travel should also be considered. Promote these modes by emphasising health benefits and in the case of (e-)bikes, efficiency.

Provide incentives for e-vehicles through subsidies and tax exemptions. Ensuring there are enough charging points and free e-parking spaces. Given the need to make room for public transport and active travel, e-mobility should not become an alternative to public transport and active travel.

Intensify cooperation with employers, schools, destinations of leisure and shopping to minimise car travel. Work together to address the poorly connected public transport and bike network (and bike parking) to these areas, and encourage schools and businesses to deliver awareness-raising campaigns. Working from home should also be considered. And the Region could plan neighbourhoods to include local shops and leisure facilities.

Integrate air quality and sustainable development into the curriculum. The success of ClairCity's schools engagements suggests that there is local interest, specifically concerning the activities and sources of pollution, and their solutions.

Work with NGOs to spread awareness. Citizen interest in air quality and carbon emissions is relatively low and limits possibilities for policy action. This might be related to a lack of knowledge. For instance, many citizens may not realise the health dangers of transport emissions.

Promote renewable energy and district heating with renewables. Support rooftop solar PV, including on public buildings and support local citizen cooperatives for renewables generation. Consider district heating alongside an awareness raising campaign to minimise resistance to change. In addition, communicate the dangers of biomass burning for air quality and health as it is often considered a sustainable fuel.

Make a long-term vision for air quality related policies and make citizen support for current and planned policies more explicit. No long-term targets and policy plans exist for air pollution or climate change on either a regional or local level, and the last available air quality plan for the Liguria Region dates from 2006. As such, updating the Regional air quality plan and developing a long-term vision should be considered. Implementation can be facilitated by a detailed year-by-year implementation plan. Communication of the citizen support for existing policies should be used to generate a wider acceptability of policies.

Reallocate/compensate costs of transport measures through revenue generating local financial instruments and communicate the need for such instruments. Authorities should consider rewarding behavioural change (e.g. discounts at local shops for bike use/rental). Meanwhile, costs of new walking/cycling infrastructure can be (partly) offset by reallocating funds currently dedicated to road infrastructure.

Use 'Improving quality of life', 'climate' and 'preserving Ligurian environment' as hooks to defend policies. Considering the 'seasonal' aspect of O₃, it is probably worth implementing transport measures affecting motorised vehicles and focusing any awareness campaigns in the summer months, when the problem is most visible.

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